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Indirect Electrochemical Determination of Niclosamide at Gold Electrode by Differential Pulse Voltammetry

Sahar A. Fathi^{1*}, Amer Th.AL-Tae¹, Nabeel S.Othman¹

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¹University of Mosul ,Chemistry Department ,College of Science, Mosul ,Iraq

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ABSTRACT

Niclosamide was determined indirectly using differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) through the reduction of diazotised niclosamide formed from the reaction of amino group in pre-reduced niclosamide with sodium nitrite in the presence of hydrochloric acid. The suggested method involved the nitro group reduction in niclosamide to group of amino by the addition of zinc powder and 1M hydrochloric acid using water bath fixed at 90°C for 15 min. The reduced niclosamide added to a three electrodes electrochemical cell containing (2.5)mL of (0.0725) M NaNO₂ and (2.5)mL of 1M HCl to form diazonium salt which is then suffer electrochemical reduction at gold electrode (AuE) as a result of applied voltage. The diazotised reduced niclosamide (RNICA) formed gives a reduction peak at -0.557V versus The reference electrode is silver/silver chloride saturated potassium chloride (Ag/AgCl/ sat. KCl). The reduction peak current is proportional to the concentration of RNICA added. Peak current versus concentration is plotted as a straight line. within concentration range [(1.0 –3.487)x10⁻⁶] M by calibration equation $I_p = 3.344c - 0.8256$ with R² value equal 0.9853. The LOD and LOQ values were 2.471x10⁻⁷ M and 8.238x10⁻⁷M respectively.

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1. Introduction

Niclosamide (NICA) is an anthelmintic active against most tapeworms, including the beef tapeworm (*Taenia saginata*), pork tapeworm (*Taenia solium*), fish tapeworm (*Diphyllobothrium latum*), and dog tapeworm (*Dipylidium caninum*); it has also been used to treat infections with the dwarf tapeworm, *Hymenolepis nana*. [1]. Niclosamide has been licensed by the FDA as an anthelmintic for 50 years; nevertheless, in the last five years, there has been a surge of interest in its usage as an anticancer drug.[2] Negative consequences Occasionally, niclosamide might cause gastrointestinal problems. Light headedness and itching [1]. Anhydrous niclosamide, thin crystals, yellowish-white or yellowish, completely insoluble in water, sparingly soluble in acetone, and

* Corresponding author: Sahar A. Fathi

E-mail address: sahar.20scp129@student.uomosul.edu.iq

faintly soluble in ethanol. Light should be avoided. 2',5-Dichloro-4'-nitrosalicylanilid; 5-Chloro-N-(2-chloro-4-nitrophenyl)-2-hydroxybenzamide C₁₃H₈Cl₂N₂O₄ =327.1 g/mol (molecular formula) [3].

Figure 1. Chemical structure of niclosamide

According to scientific literature, there are just a few electrochemical methods for determining niclosamide. Among these methods are the following: The multiple walled carbon nanotubes/cyclodextrins composite modified glassy carbon electrode (MWCNT/CD/GCE) was used to create an electrochemical sensor that was used to assess the niclosamide residual.[4]. The electrochemical oxidation behaviour of niclosamide at a glassy carbon electrode was studied using cyclic voltammetry, square-wave voltammetry, and controlled potential electrolysis.[5].For the electrocatalytic Niclosamide reduction[6], a modified electrode constructed by carbon nanoparticle/chitosan film (CNP/CS) was utilized. Spectroscopic methods for determination of niclosamide, this method depends on the nitro group reduction in niclosamide and then the reduced niclosamide interacts with N,N-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in non-aqueous media to produce a color product with a wavelength of 454 nm. [7]. The following method for determining niclosamide (NIC) is proposed reduction of niclosamide by zinc powder in acidic medium, diazotization of reduced niclosamide, and coupling with 2,6- dihydroxybenzoic acid to give a yellow colored product that is water soluble and has a maximum absorption at 456nm[8]. An indirect spectrophotometric method for determining niclosamide in pharmaceutical preparations is based on the oxidation of reduced form of niclosamide with iron (III) in acidic medium, followed by the reaction of iron (II) with 1,10-phenanthroline to produce a water-soluble ferroin complex, which is measured at 510nm[9].An HPLC technique for simultaneous measurement of anhydrous niclosamide has been developed[10]. Reversed phase high performance liquid chromatographic method for the simultaneous determination niclosamide in bulk and oral suspension for veterinary [11]. Simple and sensitive LCMS/MS assay for application in preclinical assessments of niclosamide[12].

2.EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Apparatus

Differential pulse voltametric measurement (DPV) was carried out with the aid of a 797 VA Computrace supplied by Metrohm, Switzerland, and a three-electrode detection system consisting of a gold electrode as the working electrode, A reference electrode of silver/silver chloride saturated chloride (Ag/AgCl/sat. KCl) and an auxiliary electrode of 2.0 mm platinum wire were used. pH measurements were taken with a digital pH meter supplied by the HANNA firm in Portugal, model pH211, and were accurate to 0.05.

2.2.Reagents

Reduced niclosamide solution RNICA

A concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (1.528×10^{-3} M) reduced niclosamide solution was prepared by dissolving 0.05 gm of niclosamide in 10 mL of absolute ethanol in a 50 mL beaker and using an ultrasonic device to ensure complete dissolution of niclosamide then 5 mL of 1 M hydrochloric acid and 0.1 gm of zinc powder were added, the beaker positioned in the water bath fixed at the 90°C for 15 min. with stirring the solution using magnetic bar. After cooling, the solution is filtered through filter paper and the volume is completed to 100 mL with distilled water in a volumetric flask (then diluted to 1×10^{-3} M) [3].

RNICA veterinary and pharmaceutical preparation

A 500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (1.528×10^{-3} M) reduced niclosamide solution was prepared by dissolving 0.07114 g veterinary preparation and 0.0652 g pharmaceutical of niclosamide in 10 mL of absolute ethanol using 50 mL beaker, ultrasonic device was used to obtain complete dissolution, then 5 mL of hydrochloric acid (1 M) and 0.1 g of zinc powder were added, the beaker positioned in a water bath at 90°C for 15 min., stirring also required. After cooling, the solution is filtered through filter paper and the volume is completed to 100 mL with distilled water in a volumetric flask (then diluted to 1×10^{-3} M) [3].

Britton Robinson buffer solution (B.R.B)

A pH 2.2 B.R.B solution was made by combining equal parts 0.12 M acetic acid, 0.12 M boric acid, and 0.12 M phosphoric acid.[13]

Sodium nitrite solution

0.5% concentration of sodium nitrite (NaNO_2) was made by dissolving 0.5 g of NaNO_2 in water that has been distilled and completing the volume to 100 mL in a 100 mL volumetric flask.

3.2.Recommended procedure

The suggested method involved the addition of zinc powder reduces the nitro group in niclosamide to the amino group and 1M hydrochloric acid using water bath fixed at 90°C for 15 min. The reduced niclosamide added to an electrochemical cell containing (2.5) mL of (0.0725) M NaNO_2 and (2.5) mL of 1M HCl to form diazonium salt which is then suffer electrochemical reduction at gold electrode (GE) as a result of applied voltage. The diazonium salt formed gives a reduction wave at -0.557V versus The reference electrode is silver/silver chloride saturated potassium chloride (Ag/AgCl /sat. KCl). The reduction peak current is proportional to the concentration of RNICA added. Scheme (1) shows the reduction step of niclosamide and the formation of diazonium salt [8].

Scheme 1. Steps of reaction.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The ratio of NaNO₂/HCl

To find the appropriate percentage of NaNO₂/HCl for the preparation of nitrous acid which is used to form the diazotised RNICA, different volumes of 0.5% sodium nitrite to different volumes of 1 M hydrochloric acid were examined. 5 mL of each percentage of nitrous acid was mixed with 5 ml of BRB which is used as supporting electrolyte. Two concentrations of RNICA 1.528 x10⁻⁶ and 3.049 x10⁻⁶ M were used and the voltammograms were recorded under the default parameters of the device. The result obtained (Table 1 and Figure 2) shows that the best percentage of the mixture (HCl: NaNO₂) was 1:1 due to the higher reduction current obtained.

Table 1. The effect of sodium nitrite to hydrochloric acid amounts.

No.	Conc.% NaNO ₂ : HCl	Ip(mA) of NICA 1.526x10 ⁻⁶ M	Ep(V)	Ip(mA) oRNICA 3.049x10 ⁻⁶ M	Ep(V)	pH
I	40:60		-0.509		-0.509	1.60
		1.20	1.04	1.40	1.04	
II	50:50	0.452	-0.509	0.575	-0.503	1.62
		1.05	1.07	1.116	1.06	
III	60:40	0.254	-0.521	0.347	-0.515	164
		1.08	1.09	1.05	1.07	

Figure 2. Differential pulse voltammogram using 1:1 sodium nitrite : HCl.

3.2. Optimum conditions

Various experimental and instrumental conditions were tested using 1.996×10^{-6} M RNICA, BRB pH 2.2, 1:1 NaNO₂ (0.5%) and HCl (1M) as supporting electrolyte and gold electrode as working electrode. Table(2) shows the acquired results.

Table 2. The optimum condition for 1.996×10^{-6} M RNICA

Parameters	Values
Start Potential (V)	-0.7
End Potential (V)	1.25
Pulse amplitude (V)	0.35
Pulse time (s)	0.02
Voltage step (V)	0.006
Voltage step time (s)	0.4
Cleaning potential (V)	-0.2
Cleaning time (s)	0
Deposition potential (V)	-0.9
Deposition time (s)	50
Equilibration time (s)	5
Sweep rate (V/s)	0.015

The DPV voltammograms were recorded before and after the optimum circumstances, and the resulting voltammograms are shown in Figure (3) a and b, where it is obvious that the peak current was higher under the optimum settings than under the default parameters.

Figure 3. DPV voltammograms of 1.996×10^{-6} M RNICA (a) before optimization (b) after optimization

3.3. Reduction Stability Peak

The stability of the azo group reduction peak was investigated with 1.49710^{-6} M RNICA and voltammograms were acquired under the specified optimal circumstances. Table (3) displays the acquired results. The reduced peak current is clearly consistent for 35 minutes.

Table 3. Reduction stability peak current of 1.497×10^{-6} M RNICA

Time(mins.)	EP (V)	IP (mA)
0	-0.587	3.18
5	-0.587	3.75
10	-0.593	3.90
15	-0.593	3.98
20	-0.593	3.64
25	-0.593	3.52
30	-0.587	3.95
35	-0.587	3.34

3.4. Niclosamide calibration curve

The calibration curve was built by adding a sequence addition of standard RNICA solution (10^{-3} M) and recording the voltammogram for each addition, Figure (4), under the measured optimum conditions, Table (2), the plot of peak current versus concentration gives a straight line within the concentration range [(1-3.487) 10^{-6}] M with R^2 equal to 0.9853. The LOD and LOQ values were 2.471×10^{-7} M and 8.238×10^{-7} M respectively.

Figure 5. The calibration curve of RNICA(1×10^{-3})M.

3.5 Application

The determination of Niclosamide in its veterinary and pharmaceutical preparations (tablets) was used to assess the applicability of the suggested approach. Two types of tablets were tested, one supplied from Niclosam1250 mg produced by Zagros Pharmed company, Iran and second supplied from Yomesan 500 mg produced by Bayar Vital company, Germany. The results are shown in Table (4) and (5) indicates that the values of recoveries were within the acceptable range.

Table 4. Application of the method to the veterinary preparation niclosam (Zagros Pharmed, Iran), 1250 mg / Tablet

Taken conc. M	Found conc. M	Ip Tablet(mA)	Ip pure (μ A)	Recovery **%
1.00×10^{-6}	0.956×10^{-6}	1.770	1.850	95.60
$.1497 \times 10^{-6}$	1.440×10^{-6}	3.300	3.430	96.19
1.996×10^{-6}	1.931×10^{-6}	5.040	5.210	96.74

*Average of three determinations.

Table 5. Application of the method to the pharmaceutical preparation Yomesan (Bayar Vital , German) 500 mg/Tablet.

Taken conc. of RNICA, M	Found conc. of RNICA, M	Ip Tablet(mA)	Ip pure (mA)	Recovery **%
1.00×10^{-6}	1.032×10^{-6}	1.896	1.836	103.20
$.1497 \times 10^{-6}$	1.519×10^{-6}	3.400	3.350	101.46
1.996×10^{-6}	2.012×10^{-6}	5.536	5.490	100.80

*Average of three determinations.

3.6 Precision and accuracy

For three determinations of different concentrations of RNICA solution, the accuracy and precision of the standard calibration curve were represented by relative standard deviation and relative error, and the ensuing peak currents were recorded at the previous optimal conditions. Table (6) displays the acquired results.

Table 6. Accuracy and precision values

Amount of RNICA taken M	Relative error%	Relative standard deviation*, %
1.00×10^{-6}	-1.59	1.52
1.497×10^{-6}	3.15	3.22
1.997×10^{-6}	-2.89	3.85

*Average of three determinations.

The result shows that the proposed method has good accuracy and precision.

4. Conclusion

Niclosamide can be determined indirectly through the addition of zinc powder reduces the nitro group to the amino group and 1M hydrochloric acid and the amino group formed can convert to diazonium salt by the addition of sodium nitrite with hydrochloric acid, the diazotised RNICA is easily reduced at appropriate potential, the reduction peak current is directly proportional to concentration of niclosamide added. The results demonstrate that the proposed method is accurate and precise.

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